

Supplementary Document: Neutron Radiography Imaging of Near-Field Water-air Spray at Elevated Pressures

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1. Aluminum Chamber Design

An aluminum chamber designed for elevated pressures and neutron penetration. The sample nozzle is attached to the top plate and is lowered into the chamber, suspended for operation. The chamber is designed to reach up to 8 bar pressure, gage.

Figure S1: Aluminum pressure chamber (left); Inside of cap featuring wall blowers (a), air feed (b), and water feed (c) (right). Nozzle (d) detached from feeds.

Figure S2: Post use and CT exposure nozzle. Air feed from top; water feed from side.

2. 50mL/min and 100mL/min Nozzle Flow Conditions

As stated in the primary text, multiple flow conditions were tested with 10slpm of air for 30 second exposures. Here the 50mL/min and 100mL/min results not shown in the primary text are given. This shows the effects of injection flow rate on the spray characteristics and water density present at the varying chamber pressures.

2.i 50 mL/min water

Figure S3: Normalized neutron images captured by the camera. Water flow at 50 mL/min mixed with 10 slpm of air between 0 and 5 Bar gage chamber pressures.

Figure S4: Background and active spray images captured over 30 seconds, radioed (I/I_0) and filtered to show spray characteristics. The conditions for the images shown are 50 mL/min of water mixed with 10 slpm of air at pressures between 0 and 5 Bar gage.

Figure S5: Region of interest (ROI) at the atomizing nozzle exit. Water flow rate at 50 mL/min mixed with 10 slpm air. Water density shown varies up to 300 kg/m³.

2.ii 100 mL/min water

Figure S6: Normalized neutron images captured by the camera. Water flow at 100 mL/min mixed with 10 slpm of air between 0 and 5 Bar gage chamber pressures.

Figure S7: Background and active spray images captured over 30 seconds, radioed (I/I_0) and filtered to show spray characteristics. The conditions for the images shown are 100 mL/min of water mixed with 10 slpm of air at pressures between 0 and 5 Bar gage.

Figure S8: Region of interest (ROI) at the atomizing nozzle exit. Water flow rate at 80 mL/min mixed with 10 slpm air. Water density shown varies up to 300 kg/m^3 .

3. 3D Tomography of the Atomizing Nozzle

As mentioned in the primary text, the nozzle was subject to a CT-scan from 0 to 360° rotation, capturing a 30 second image every 0.31° of rotation. Using the software Amira, of which access was permitted through analysis nodes at Oak Ridge National Laboratory, the images were stitched together to produce the 3-dimensional tomography of the nozzle. For the 6 second 3D

video clip, the nozzle body was made mostly transparent and the high attenuation areas where water is present were highlighted. This is to show the geometry of the nozzle as captured by neutron imaging.

Rotation.mpg

File S1: 6 second video rotating and zooming into the geometries highlighted by water attenuation in the nozzle.